

Appraisal of the Freedom of Information Act and its Influence on Investigative Journalism in Nigeria

Iliya Jeremiah Ovey; Prof. Muhammad Sani Rabiou & Tsegyu Santas, PhD

Department of Mass Communication, Faculty of Communication and Media Studies
Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

jeremiahiliyaovey@nsuk.edu.ng; rabiums123@gmail.com; tsegyu@nsuk.edu.ng

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Abstract

The Freedom of Information Act enhances transparency in governance by serving as a support system in the fight against corruption and other ills in society. The Act holds those in power accountable through transparent access to information and records. This is reinforced by practices such as investigative journalism, which digs into the records of government agencies and officeholders to unearth information. The researchers assessed the impact of the Freedom of Information Act on investigative journalism by critically examining its effectiveness, challenges and prospects for investigative journalists in promoting press freedom in Nigeria from 2011 to 2025. Anchored on the social responsibility and agenda setting theories, the study is qualitative, as it relied on secondary data. It revealed that the FOI Act has effectively impacted investigative journalism; although, there are many challenges bedeviling its smooth operations. Issues such as institutional barriers and the government's bureaucracy are hindering the Act's full implementation. The researchers concluded that although the FOIA has established a legal framework for accessing public information by investigative journalists with considerable prospects, its implementation in Nigeria remains inadequate due to restricted access, threats and a lack of institutional support, among other problems.

Keywords: Journalism, Investigative Journalism, Freedom of Information Act, Transparency, Accountability

Introduction

Journalism is very important in every society. This is because journalists, through their information, education and socialisation functions, play a key role by acting as societal watchdogs (Ituma *et al* 2019). Information can be equated with power (Obi & Mmejim, 2019) and is fundamental to every human right in society (Senam *et al* 2017). Kemp & Fry, in Okunna & Popoola (2017), align with the notion that the media and journalists are key societal actors. Oko-Epelle *et al* (2023) also agree that by professional standards, journalists should be able to gather and report events, including conducting investigations, gathering facts and expressing opinions freely. Hence, Asogwa *et al* (2021) assert that the Freedom of Information Act is crucial in society as it was created to promote democracy, transparency and accountability in governance.

Investigative journalism serves as one of the bedrocks of democratic governance, with salient emphasis on accountability and transparency. The Freedom of Information Act of 2011 in Nigeria was introduced to provide access to government-held information. However, the interplay between investigative journalism and the FOI Act remains complex (Olaniyan, 2021; Adeyemi, 2019). According to Uche in Mohammed (2022, p. 2), the media and government in Nigeria operate in a “cat and mouse affair” pattern of connection. Hence, in their quest for in-depth and objective reporting, media professionals, such as investigative journalists seeking materials to report to the public, are most of the time vulnerable to victimisation, jail, torture and sometimes death (Ezeah in Ituma *et al* 2019). Therefore, this paper assessed the impact of the Freedom of Information Act on investigative journalism in Nigeria, evaluating its effectiveness, challenges and prospects from 2011 to 2025.

Conceptual Clarification of Investigative Journalism

Investigative journalism, often regarded as one of the cornerstones of journalistic practice, involves a systematic, in-depth inquiry into matters of public interest. It typically exposes wrongdoing, corruption, abuse of power or institutional failures that would otherwise remain hidden from the public. According to Aucoin (2004), investigative journalism has been labelled with various names such as "watchdog journalism," "muckraking," and "public service journalism." These concepts all emphasise the adversarial and socially responsible character of this type of journalism.

Dyikuk (2017) describes investigative journalism as a form of journalism that relies on non-routine information-gathering methods to uncover the truth, which requires extensive research, data analysis, source verification, and sometimes undercover techniques to obtain credible evidence. Asemah (2011) notes that such reporting is time-consuming and often poses risks to the journalist due to the sensitive nature of the information being pursued. Hasan (2013) observes that the ultimate aim of investigative journalism is to empower the public by unveiling concealed realities, particularly those involving criminal, political or corporate misconduct in society.

Furthermore, Dominick (cited in Asemah, 2009) defines investigative journalism as a technique that employs non-conventional methods to gather information that holds public significance. Consequently, this form of journalism distinguishes itself from daily news coverage by its depth, exclusivity, and long-term societal impact. This is one of the reasons why Ahmad, Ismail, & Mustapha (2014) posit that investigative journalism remains a powerful tool for public enlightenment and reform when backed by legal frameworks like the Freedom of Information Act.

Understanding Freedom of Information (FOI)

Freedom of Information is a democratic principle rooted in the belief that access to public records is essential for transparency, civic engagement and the realisation of human rights. FOI ensures that citizens, journalists and civil society organisations have the legal right to

request, receive and disseminate information held by government institutions and public bodies. Locke as cited in Bhargava & Ashok (2008) argues that freedom “is an inalienable right that includes the liberty to access knowledge critical to one’s wellbeing and participation in society” (p.43). Udoudo *et al* (2020) also explain that FOI promotes informed citizenship, encourages constructive debate, and holds government accountable through public oversight. Mendel in Udombana (2019) affirms that FOI laws reduce information imbalance by providing the legal basis for the right to know, regardless of the petitioner's intent or status.

Freedom of Information is, therefore, a cornerstone of democratic governance, enabling citizens to access vital information that affects their lives. As Onuegbu & Anunike (2024) assert, when properly implemented, FOI frameworks enhance transparency, build trust in institutions, and deepen participatory democracy.

Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) in Nigeria

The Freedom of Information Act (FOI), passed into law in Nigeria in 2011, as defined by Oduah (2015), allows individuals, upon request, free access to public records for public interest, provided there are no adverse consequences. Odunlami (2020) notes that the FOI Act comprises 32 sections designed to safeguard public records while protecting individual privacy. The Act specifies the various processes for seeking information as well as exemptions that come with it, like in the case of national security and protection of journalism sources (s. 16), among others. Additionally, ROLAC (2023) emphasises that the FOI Act enhances citizens' access to information and strengthens government accountability.

The Freedom of Information Act is applicable to all federal institutions and agencies in Nigeria, as they are required to provide requested information about official documents like contracts, budgets, and other official correspondence. Except for the few ones that are legally exempted (Mohammed *et al* 2023). Udombana (2019) stresses that the Act does not require the requester to demonstrate any specific interest in the information being sought, thereby expanding its accessibility to all citizens. Furthermore, the FOI Act includes clauses that protect whistleblowers and public servants who release information in good faith. Despite its progressive features, the implementation of the FOI Act in Nigeria has faced substantial challenges, including non-compliance by public institutions, hectic bureaucratic processes and weak enforcement mechanisms (Agba, Ogri & Adomi, 2018). Therefore, Odunlami (2020) notes that many public officials are either unaware of the FOI Act or deliberately resisting compliance, which limits its intended power.

Transparency and Accountability

Transparency and accountability are foundational principles in public administration and democratic governance. Transparency refers to the openness and availability of information about government processes, decisions and expenditures. It ensures that

public institutions operate in a manner that is visible and understandable to citizens. Jashari & Pepaj (2018) define transparency as the willingness of institutions to share information proactively and respond to information requests promptly. It involves a commitment to openness in all dealings, particularly in areas such as budgeting, procurement and public service delivery. Hence, institutional credibility and public trust are mostly built when there are robust FOI Act frameworks that support transparency in governance.

Accountability deals with the onus on public officers to explicitly share and explain their activities and actions to the people in society. It is valuable in all democratic societies because it enhances investigative journalism through the environment for moral and legal laws. Journalists who indulge in investigative reporting are promoting accountability by exposing misconduct like corruption (McQuail, 2010). Ackerman & Sandoval (2006) also posit that one of the core objectives of the Freedom of Information Act is to promote participatory democracy and increase government accountability by creating a mutual understanding between the people and the government. These principles enable oversight as they reduce loopholes that promote corruption in government. The connection between transparency and accountability mostly works when there are viable frameworks that support strong legal backings, a watchful media and a knowledgeable populace.

Review of Literature

Several authors have tried to examine the impact of the Freedom of Information Act on journalism practice in Nigeria. According to Obayi *et al* (2020) and Inokoba (2014), the cardinal objectives of the FOI Act in Nigeria are to improve the culture of transparent record-keeping and disclosure as well as boost accountability in government operations. It also protects sources and other whistleblowers who may divulge certain information to reporters and the public. The Act is generally designed to counter restrictive laws that endorse total secrecy in governance.

The Freedom of Information Act has created a legal opportunity for journalists, especially those conducting investigations, to hold the government accountable by seeking records and other relevant information. Folarin (2005) observes that there can never be transparency and accountability without a viable investigative journalism backed by a strong Freedom of Information law, because it keeps the government on its toes by subjecting its processes to public scrutiny. It is on this premise that Ojebode & Azeez (2018) underscore the importance of FOI laws and investigative journalism in suppressing corruption in democratic nations. Gever & Santas (2015) equally espoused that the FOI has empowered not only the journalists but ordinary citizens as well.

The FOI Act protects key areas such as national security records and transnational issues, including the right to discretion, law enforcement materials, commercial or financial information, and court proceedings. Section 16 of the Act provides a clear argument for the defence of professionals such as health workers, legal practitioners, and

journalists. Apuke (2016) argues that with this FOI Act, journalists and civil societies without fear or favour are expected to investigate more societal issues, especially governance, and report corruption, misconduct, embezzlement, misappropriation of funds, and every form of abuse in the practice of civic management.

Consequently, familiarity with the FOI Act significantly enhances professionalism in a journalist's investigative stories. Journalists who have a deep understanding of the Act can effectively research and conduct thorough investigations. This is because fact-finding (investigative) journalism serves as a cornerstone of journalistic practice. Ahmad & Nasir (2022) emphasise that the essence of investigative journalism is to address social issues such as corruption, terrorism, and drug abuse, among others. Investigative reporters also seek to expose issues related to wrongdoing, crime, and corruption, which often impact society within both public and private organisations (Antai & Umoren, 2023). A high knowledge of the FOI Act will boost the quality of a reporter's investigative story.

However, Adeyemi (2019) observes that despite the enactment of the FOI in 2011 by Goodluck Jonathan's regime, many government agencies in Nigeria are still reluctant to release information, often leveraging administrative bureaucracy and intimidation of journalists, which in turn affects investigative journalism. Antai & Umoren 2023; Obinna 2019; Mohammed *et al* 2023; Mohammed 2022; Udombana 2019 and Agba *et al* (2018) all note that despite the presence of the Act, its implementation and use are still a mirage. Agba *et al* (2018) further point out ignorance, denial of access by officials, executive immunity, exclusion of the private sector, and rigid legal processes as some of the major challenges obstructing the smooth operation of the FOI Act.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored on the social responsibility theory and the agenda setting theory to analyse the influence of the Freedom of Information Act on investigative journalism in Nigeria.

The agenda setting theory by McCombs & Shaw (1972) argues that media influences public perception by highlighting certain issues, making them seem more important based on the attention they receive. That is, the first assumption of this theory is that the media shapes public discourse by choosing which issues to report to the public. The second assumption rests on the fact that more media attention increases the perceived importance of an issue in society.

The major nitty-gritty here, according to McCombs (2004), is that the media is important for exposing corruption and raising awareness of key issues. Investigative journalism helps reveal governance failures and human rights abuses. In Nigeria, investigative journalists use the Freedom of Information Act provisions to access documents and shape public discussion. On the other hand, McQuail (2010) notes that the social responsibility theory was postulated to correct the pitfalls of the libertarian press theory, as it focuses on the media's duty to serve the public and support democracy. The

proponents of this theory suggest the media can operate freely but require some government oversight (Baran & Davis, 2013). Consequently, Asemah *et al* (2017) observe that the social responsibility theory promotes media diversity (such as multiplicity in information sources), quality content, public order, and the empowerment of marginalised groups, while emphasising the responsibility of both media workers and audiences.

In the ideal sense, the social responsibility theory states that journalists must act ethically and provide clear and fair information. In this case, the Freedom of Information Act is mostly effective for investigative journalism because it grants reporters access to records and information, which promotes accurate information aimed at exposing the wrongdoings in society. This also holds the government accountable to the people.

The agenda-setting and social responsibility theories are important to this study because both are critical for understanding the impacts, challenges and opportunities of the FOI Act in influencing investigative journalism in Nigeria. The agenda-setting theory shows how journalism influences public issues by generating discourse on serious issues, while the social responsibility theory underscores journalists' ethical duty to inform the public. Both theories are necessary in appraising the influence of the FOI Act in Nigeria, as it succinctly highlights the need for better protection for investigative journalists and full compliance with the provisions of the Act.

Methodology

This study uses secondary data from different studies. Hence, books, official documents and other published and unpublished works were utilised for the study.

Discussion

Nigeria's Freedom of Information Act, enacted 2011 was designed to protect records, promote transparency and accountability, and enhance public access to information. Amponsah (2024, p.2) asserts that journalism is a vital aspect of democratic governance, stating, "investigative journalism represents a valuable tool to provide the public with the best protection from the excesses of state power and individual or institutional exploitative actions and omissions that undermine societal good." Also, Zuffova (2021) emphasises that freedom laws cultivate an environment where journalists can thrive in their watchdog roles. Under these laws, reporters have the freedom to seek and convey the truth to the government, utilising tips and information obtained from sources. FOI laws empower journalists to request records and information from those in power without the fear of retribution.

However, the key connection between the Freedom of Information Act, as a legal document, and investigative journalism in Nigeria can be seen in two ways. First, the FOI Act strengthens accountability and transparency in governance. Investigative journalists take advantage of the provisions of the FOI Act to demand information from the

government, thereby promoting accountability in governance by exposing issues like corruption, which contributes to an informed public.

Secondly, the Freedom of Information also improves access to information for investigative journalism by enabling journalists to seek official records and other documents to enhance their story's credibility. Records obtained from official sources are more reliable as they enhance the depth of investigative reports by providing accurate and thorough references to issues. As a catalyst for investigative journalism in Nigeria, the Freedom of Information Act is designed to foster transparency and empower citizens, including journalists, to access public records. Since the passage of the bill into an Act over 14 years ago, investigative journalists have been using it to expose abuse of power, corruption and other mismanagement in Nigeria. The FOI Act has provided Nigerian investigative journalists with a constitutional tool to demand transparency from public institutions. Investigative journalists have used the Act to unveil corruption, inefficiency, and human rights violations.

Notable examples include Taiwo Hassan Adebayo, who used the Act to access records for investigations on railway contract fraud during the regimes of Goodluck Jonathan and Muhammadu Buhari (GIJN, 2023). Another significant example includes Fisayo Soyombo of the Foundation for Investigative Journalism (FIJ), who combined the FOI Act with undercover journalism to investigate corruption in Nigeria's criminal justice system. *The Cable* newspaper reported that Soyombo, in the investigative journey disguised as an inmate to access police and correctional service records to unearth discrepancies in their operations (*The Cable*, 2019).

The *Daily Nigerian* Newspaper in 2023 published a report by Umar Audu, who worked undercover to uncover corruption in the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC). The investigative report, according to Ovey *et al* (2024), shook the country as it revealed how some syndicates were cheaply selling fake degree certificates from the Benin Republic and other neighbouring countries to interested buyers, to process for the NYSC scheme. Similarly, another investigative story leveraging the FOI Act by Salihu Ayatullahi exposed illegal mining in Kwara State by revealing how Chinese companies bribed government officials to secure mining sites and other waivers. Another of Ayatullahi's investigations also exposed how votes were manipulated during elections by some officials (ICIR, 2023). Aside from these success stories, civic tech platforms like the Dataphyte have also been using the FOI Act to unravel corruption in the country (Dataphyte, 2020).

These pieces of investigation were crucial to the fight against corruption as they demonstrate the media's watchdog functions of reporting credible and accurate stories, prompting increased pressure on public officials and institutions. Just as Ojebode & Azeez (2018) observed, the existence of the FOI Act has emboldened journalists to challenge the secrecy often associated with Nigerian governance, especially regarding budget allocations and public procurement. Apuke (2016) also notes that the FOI Act has

potentially transformed journalism into a more fact-based, data-driven, and socially impactful profession.

Challenges in Using the FOI Act for Investigative Journalism

Despite the presence of the FOI Act in supporting investigative journalism in Nigeria, there are some barriers to the effective use of the Act. The first barrier can be attributed to the decline of investigative journalism. In the present time, the culture of investigative journalism in Nigeria is becoming weak. The few investigative journalists and media outlets engaged in this practice are walking on tightropes due to pressure and persecution. Although, this is somehow a global issue (Antai & Umoren, 2023), Nnanwuba *et al* (2019) note that a poor culture of investigative journalism in Nigeria is negatively affecting the utilisation of the Freedom of Information (FOI) Act among media practitioners.

Uzoma & Onwukwe (cited in Nnanwuba *et al* 2019) further observe that without consistent practice of investigative journalism, reporters would hardly have any serious need for information that is kept from the public and which the journalist should request for its release. The implication is that the FOI Act may seem useless to journalists, thereby affecting the primary goals of the Act. It is important to establish the fact that this development has affected media roles of providing accountability in Nigeria's democratic system (Santas & Ogoshi, 2016).

There is also a challenge of systemic and institutional complications. Despite its potential, FOI Act implementation in Nigeria is hindered by systemic obstacles. Many public institutions routinely deny access to information or delay responses beyond the seven-day limit prescribed by law (FOIA, 2011; MRA, 2022). Udombana (2019) maintains that government agencies often exploit the broad and vague exemptions under sections like those protecting "national security" or "commercial interests" to reject requests without meaningful justification. According to a 2022 Media Rights Agenda (MRA) assessment report, only 28.5% of FOI Act requests by journalists received responses within the stipulated legal timeframe, while nearly 50% were ignored entirely (MRA, 2022). This pattern of bureaucratic obstruction weakens the core principle of the FOI Act and frustrates journalistic inquiry, such as a robust investigative journalism practice. Like Adeyemi (2019) notes, the impacts of the FOI Act have been reduced by poor enforcement, lack of political will, and corruption within public offices. Furthermore, ignorance among public officials, executive immunity claims, and deliberate suppression of information are widespread, rendering the FOI Act a theory rather than a practical tool in many contexts (Agba *et al* 2018).

Another major impediment to investigative journalism in Nigeria is the issue of harassment and intimidation of investigative journalists because of the harsh environment in which they operate. Investigative journalists frequently face intimidation, threats, and even imprisonment. This development portends danger to Nigeria democracy, especially when the country is expected to consolidate governance at current time (Santas, 2014).

For example, the Committee to Protect Journalists (CPJ, 2023) documented numerous cases where journalists were detained or harassed for filing FOI Act requests or publishing investigative stories. Usman (2023) cited the case of Omoyele Sowore, publisher of Sahara Reporters in 2020, who was arrested and detained for publishing reports critical of government corruption. His case is one of many where the FOI Act, rather than protecting journalists, failed to shield them from state retaliation. Such threats often affect press freedom. According to Antai & Umoren (2023), fear of reprisal or victimisation discourages journalists from pursuing FOI-based investigations, especially in states with politically entrenched elites or security-linked corruption.

There is also a case of underutilisation of the FOI Act by investigative journalists. It is pertinent to note that while the FOI Act's document is open and accessible to all Nigerians, many journalists are still not familiar with it. According to Ahmed & Idi (2024), a good number of journalists in Nigeria have limited knowledge of the operations of the FOI Act, which affects their ability to use the provisions to legally seek information. While for Journalists who are familiar with the laws, Nnanwuba *et al* (2019) observe that most of them are hesitant to utilise the Freedom of Information (FOI) Act due to legal, political factors, and a weak investigative journalism culture. Consequently, the FOI Act document is not popular in most newsrooms and many reporters, including some who are conducting investigations, lack the proper orientation on how to utilise the Act. Some journalists and media organisations also forfeit good investigations due to financial constraints to legally fight when their rights are violated. When information is denied, instead of going to court, the reporters abandon the search because of money to pursue litigation in courts, thereby encumbering the media's watchdog roles (Okoro & Ugwuanyi, 2021).

In comparing the full implementation of the Freedom of Information Act with other African countries, studies have shown that Nigeria is still struggling to adapt to the culture of effectively using the Act. African countries like South Africa and Ghana are enjoying a more responsive FOI practice. Institutions in both countries comply and respond faster to requests for information. They also have bodies that oversee and punish noncompliance with requests for information using the FOI Act (Banda, 2021; Fosu, 2022). This, to an extent, enhances transparency and accountability in their governance as public records and information are legally made available at any time. In contrast, Nigeria is still struggling to create and maintain a dedicated enforcement body to oversee the Act's implementation. As Eze & Bello (2022) point out, the absence of accountability measures for non-compliant agencies renders the FOI Act weak in practice.

Prospects in Using the FOI Act for Investigative Journalism in Nigeria

So far, there are signs of progress in the effort to promote the use of the FOI Act by journalists and Nigerians. In April 2025, the Supreme Court of Nigeria ruled that the FOI Act applies at both federal and state levels, thereby resolving years of uncertainty where some state institutions claimed exemption from the Act (*FOICOUNSEL*, 2025). This

ruling has the potential to expand access to critical information, especially at the state and local government levels, which could be more corrupt. This decision could pave the way for wider applicability and stronger institutional accountability across all the executive, legislative and judicial tiers of government in Nigeria.

Moreover, the rise of digital journalism and data-driven reporting presents a new frontier for the FOI Act utility. Platforms like Premium Times, The Cable and Dataphyte continue to push the boundaries of investigative journalism to bypass traditional media constraints (Okoro & Ugwuanyi, 2021). Social media have also emerged as a valuable means for sharing FOI Act findings, generating public debate and mobilising civic action. However, digital progress is not without setbacks. The Nigerian government has introduced cybercrime and hate speech laws that critics argue are used to suppress online dissent and FOIA-based revelations (CPJ, 2023; Amadi & Ojo, 2021).

It is safer to say, while the Freedom of Information Act in Nigeria has created new possibilities for investigative journalism, its success is undermined by poor implementation, limited legal enforcement, harassment of journalists and inadequate institutional support. Nonetheless, judicial backing, digital innovation, and increased media literacy offer avenues for strengthening FOI Act usage and promoting accountability.

Conclusion

The Freedom of Information Act has undoubtedly opened new pathways for investigative journalism in Nigeria, providing a legal framework to demand transparency and accountability in governance. However, the potential of the FOIA remains underutilised due to a host of systemic and institutional barriers. Investigative journalists often face resistance, threats and a lack of institutional support when seeking access to public records. Despite showing promising success stories by investigative reporters, barriers like resistance, threats and poor support (cooperation from sources) have limited the use of the Act, leading to inconsistent implementation and enforcement issues. Nonetheless, there is growing momentum toward reform, especially with the Supreme Court's recent ruling that extends FOIA's applicability to all government tiers. Digital platforms and emerging data journalism initiatives are also expanding the boundaries of investigative journalism. If these developments are properly harnessed, the FOIA can fulfil its objectives as one of the cornerstones of Nigeria's democratic governance.

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